

COUNSELLING STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING LOW SELF-ESTEEM AMONG IN-SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS AS EXPRESSED BY SECONDARY SCHOOL COUNSELLORS IN KWARA STATE

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Abstract

Low self-esteem is a psychological, social, cultural and mental health problem which negatively impacts adolescents' emotional well-being, social interaction and academic performance which is currently creating a lot of concerns to guidance counsellors, psychologists and mental health practitioners in the world. This paper therefore investigated counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State. A researcher designed questionnaire entitled "Counselling Strategies for Enhancing Low Self-esteem Questionnaire (CSELSQ)" was used to collect necessary data for the study. A reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. Data analysis was done using percentage, mean and ranking order, t-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT). The study revealed the major causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents to be failure to meet others' expectations, comparison with others and parental social economic status among others. The counselling strategies mostly adopted by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State are person-centered, group, and cognitive behaviour therapies. Hypothesis one, two and three were rejected. The study therefore recommended amongst others that Seminars, workshop and conferences should be organized for secondary school counsellors to enable them utilize the various counselling strategies in enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents to a great extent.

Keywords: *Low Self-Esteem, Counselling Strategies, Secondary School Counsellors, In-school Adolescents*

Introduction

Self-esteem refers to the overall evaluation and perception of one's abilities, encompassing self-confidence, respect, and acceptance, influencing an individual's attitudes, and behaviours, and interactions with others. An individual self-esteem can either be high or low. High self-esteem refers to a positive and realistic perception of oneself which is characterized by confidence, self-

respect, and self-acceptance. Individuals with low self-esteem feels inadequate and worthless, views themselves as inferior and unable to generate inner resources to improve the situation. Therefore, feeling of inferiority may result when one does not meet up to personal aspirations (Nwokolo & Oguzie, 2021). Low self-esteem involves constant self-doubt, self-criticism, social anxiety and isolation, suppressed anger, loneliness, and shame; in-school adolescents with low self-esteem tend to perceive themselves and issues of life in a more negative and critical light, they also feel unable to handle the challenges of life (Okafor, et al. 2018).

Transition from adolescence to adulthood is a crucial phase of any individual's life. During this phase, an in-school adolescent face many problems and many at times it becomes very strenuous to maintain optimal level of self-esteem and collective self-esteem (Sharma & Agarwala, 2015). Majority of students in secondary schools are majorly adolescents who are faced with developmental metamorphosis accompanied by physiological and psychological tendencies with subsequent result to stress, perplexities, ambiguities and complexities (Anagbogu & Ahiaogu, 2019). The study on in-school adolescents is important because this age group is undergoing physical, emotional, and cognitive development which can have a lasting impact on their well-being and future outcomes.

Low self-esteem among in-school adolescents can emanate from the following: child abuse and punishment, peer relationship, parenting style, academic achievement, financial and social position, negligence, comparison with others, preferential treatment, excessive criticism, expectations from parents, physical appearance, bullying, ill health and negative experience (Jones, 2012). The ability of parents, caregivers, and other family members to provide adequate social support, in particular, is consistently linked to high self-esteem among in-school adolescents. In-school adolescents who report high levels of family cohesiveness, trust, and intimacy also report improved behavioural and mental health outcomes (Kibuthu, & Muasa, 2023). In contrary, low self-esteem has also been linked to uncaring, uninvolved parents who do not care about their teenagers. Many in-school adolescents also lack the right parental support, which has a significant impact on how they view themselves (Kuboka, 2017).

Guidance and counselling as a psychological intervention aims to achieve behaviour change, enhance coping skills, promote decision making, improve relationship and to facilitate in-school adolescents potentials (Dhami, 2020). Professionally trained school counsellors can implement a comprehensive school counselling program that promotes and enhances students' achievement (Mathwasa & Sibanda, 2020). School counsellors therefore, can help enhance in-school adolescents with low self-esteem by providing counselling sessions to address underlying issues, build social skills and self- confidence, implementing positive reinforcement techniques to boost their self-esteem.

On the ground of personality according to Saarnio (2010), female counsellors are keener on working motivational intervention. They have been found to be more tolerant and accepting during counselling session by displaying unconditional positive regards, than male counsellors who show more sensitivity to gender regarding behaviour and outlook towards clients. Against this concern, Devon (2023) opined that the best predictor of whether a therapy is successful is the connection the counsellor and the client create or share and not the gender.

Counsellors' experience might be essential for internalizing clients under certain circumstances. But the years of work experience do not guarantee an increase in one's expertise and personal development in counselling practice according to Konstam, et al (2015). The school counsellors are certified educators who help to improve students all round success by implementing the school counselling program, collaborate with teachers and parents to create supportive school environment (Lawal, et al. 2021). The counsellors' work experience or years in service and educational background may affect their work engagement according to Hoti (2019) and Jayanthi, et al (2020). School counsellors, therefore may seek means of enhancing self-esteem through therapeutic interventions, such as cognitive behaviour therapy, assertiveness training, person-centered therapy, psychodynamic therapy as well as group therapy.

Several studies have been carried out on strategies in enhancing low self-esteem. For example, Nwankwo, et al (2016) carried out a study on effect of cognitive behaviour therapy (CBT) on low self-esteem among secondary school students in Delta State. The finding of the study showed that cognitive behaviour therapy was effective in improving the student's low self-esteem. Okoie, et al (2015) investigated the effect of assertiveness training and cognitive restructuring technique on self-esteem of female undergraduate victims of relationship violence in south-west Nigeria. The result showed a significant main effect of treatment in the pre-post self-esteem scores of female undergraduate victims of relationship violence in the experimental and control groups.

Person-centered or Client-centered therapy helps to make the most out of a safe supportive environment in order to explore thoughts, feelings and experiences without fear of criticism or rejection which freely and openly, lead to greater self-acceptance according to Ridley (2023). Psychodynamic therapy helps an in-school adolescent figure out reasons he or she has a harsh inner critic which develop in childhood, with parents or authority figures usually being the source of them. For instance, childhood experiences which include trauma, abuse, and neglect can lead to issues in later life, such as low self-worth, a lack of self-confidence, and self-criticism (Woolfe, 2019). Group therapy is also beneficial because it provides a safe and supportive environment where individuals can openly discuss their feelings and experiences with others who are dealing with similar issues (Mao, 2019; Karibi-Whyte, 2024).

The existing literature highlights the significance of evidenced based interventions such as person-centered therapy, group therapy, assertiveness training, psychodynamic therapy and cognitive behaviour therapy. However, there is a dearth of research exploring the specific counselling strategies employed by secondary school counsellors in addressing low self-esteem among adolescents. This study aimed to bridge the gap by investigating the counselling strategies used by secondary school counsellors to enhance low self-esteem among in-school adolescents, providing valuable insights for future interventions and research.

Statement of the Problem

The goal of education is beyond making individuals acquire knowledge and skills but also to make individuals worthy in character. Low self-esteem as a prevalent issue among in-school adolescents with potential long-term consequences has been a concern among educational stakeholders. These negative consequences of low self-esteem include emotional consequences such as anxiety, depression, fear of failure, self-doubt and uncertainty; behavioural consequences

include procrastination and. lack of motivation, self-sabotaging behaviours, addictions; social consequences involves difficulty forming and maintaining relationships, social isolations and loneliness, conflict and communication issues; physical consequences include weakened immune system, sleeplessness and fatigue, digestive problems and chronic pain, eating disorders; cognitive consequences include negative self-talk, and self-criticism, lack of self-confidence and self-talk among others. The moment in-school adolescents seem to be unruly in the school, counsellors are adjudged to lack counselling skills. Thus, this study aimed at employing counselling strategies to enhance the low self-esteem of in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State?
2. What are the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on years in service.
3. There is no significant difference in counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on educational qualification.

Research Methodology

The descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The Population for this study comprised all (1003) practicing school counsellors in Kwara State (Ministry of Education and Human Capital Development, 2025). With reference to the research advisor (2006), a sample of 291 respondents was recommended for a population of this magnitude. In order to cater for attrition, 5% (5 multiply by $291/100 = 15$) of the sample size was added to make a total of 306 respondents. At the first stage, purposive sampling technique was used to select practicing secondary school counsellors from the three senatorial districts in Kwara State; Kwara North, Kwara Central and Kwara South. At stage two, proportional sampling technique was used to select school counsellors in each of the senatorial districts.

Table 1: Selection of School Counsellors in each Senatorial District in Kwara State

S/N	Senatorial District	Population	Selected Sample Size
1.	Kwara Central	512	156
2.	Kwara South	290	88
3.	Kwara North	201	61
	Grand Total	1003	306

Source: Ministry of Education, Human and Capital Development, 2025

At the third stage, simple random sampling method was used to select the secondary school counsellors during the training program organized by the Association of Professional Counsellors (APROCON) Kwara State chapter on counselling for value orientation and positive behaviour in schools (2025).

Instrumentation

Data was collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled “Counselling Strategies for Enhancing Low Self-esteem Questionnaire” (CSELSQ). The questionnaire was divided into three sections. Section A contained the demographic information of the respondents. Section B was designed to elicit information on the causes of low self-esteem and section C, contained strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents. To determine the validity of the instrument, the draft of the questionnaire was given to five experts in the Department of Educational Guidance and counselling University of Ilorin who were involved in the process of validating the instrument. The modification and comments made by these experts were considered in the final selection of items on the questionnaire.

The researchers adopted the test-retest method. Where 20 copies of the questionnaire were administered on twenty (20) school counsellors who were not part of the study and it was readministered after a period of three weeks. The two groups’ scores were correlated using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) formula. The correlation coefficient obtained for the scale was 0.81 at 0.05 alpha level which is high enough and reliable. The data gathered were analyzed using percentages, mean and ranking order analysis while t-test was used to analyze hypotheses 1 and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze hypotheses 2 and 3 at 0.05 level of significance while Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to identify which group showed the significant differences.

Results

Demographic data

A total of 306 questionnaire forms were administered but 290 were properly filled and accounted for and then used for analysis in this study. This section presents the results of data obtained from the respondents in frequency and percentages.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Demographic Data

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender		
Male	79	27.2
Female	211	72.8
Total	290	100
Years in Service		
1-5 years	36	12.4
6-10 years	61	21.0
11 years and above	193	66.6
Total	290	100
Educational qualification		
1 st Degree	265	91.4
2 nd Degree	21	7.2
3 rd Degree	4	1.4
Total	290	100

Table 1 indicates that for gender, 79 (27.2%) were male while 211 (72.8%) were female, this implies that female respondents were more than male with 211(72.8%); for years in service, 36 (12.4%) respondents had spent 1-5 years in service, 61 (21.0%) of the respondents had spent 6-10 years in service while 193 (66.6%) had already spent 11 years and above in service, this implies that counselors with 11 years in service were more than others with 193(66.6%); for educational qualification, 265 (91.4%) of the respondents had their 1st Degree certificate; 21(7.2%) had their 2nd degree certificate while 4 (1.4%) had their 3rd degree certificate respectively in educational guidance and counselling. This implies that respondents with 1st degree were more than others.

Research Question 1: *What are the causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State?*

Table 2: Means and Rank order Analysis on the causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State.

S/N	Causes of Low Self-esteem	Mean Score	S.D	Rank
3.	failure to meet others' expectations	2.9034	.894	1 st
9.	comparison with others	2.8310	.949	2 nd
6.	parental social economic status	2.8207	1.00	3 rd
4.	parenting styles	2.7966	.986	4 th
10.	negative body image	2.7241	.991	5 th
2.	critical experiences such as abuse, bullying neglect and punishment by parents and significant others	2.6966	.965	6 th
5.	inability to cope academically	2.6897	1.04	7 th
7.	religion discrimination	2.6552	.954	8 th
8.	health challenge	2.6103	.964	9 th
1.	gender	2.6069	1.02	10 th

Table 2 presents the mean and rank order on the causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State. The table indicates that item 3 (with mean score of 2.90), item 9 (with mean score of 2.83) and item 6 (with mean score of 2.82) were ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively. These items stated that “Failure to meet others’ expectations”, “Comparison with others” and “Parental social economic status” are the major causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State.

However, item 7 (with mean score of 2.65), item 8 (with mean score of 2.61) and item 1 (with mean score of 2.60) were ranked 8th, 9th and 10th respectively. The items stated that “religion discrimination”, “health challenge and “gender” respectively were the least causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State. Since all the items have mean scores that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, this implies that all the items were causes of low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State.

Research Question 2. *What are the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the counselling strategies (employing cognitive behaviour therapy, assertiveness training techniques, person-centered therapy, psychodynamics therapy and group therapy for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents in Kwara State.

S/N	Items	Mean Score	Rank
11.	to identify thought patterns that influence their low self-esteem	2.7000	
12.	to gently challenge their negative thoughts and behaviors	2.7897	
13.	to make efforts towards reframing/ redirecting negative thoughts patterns	2.7172	
	Average Mean: Cognitive Behaviour Therapy	2.735	3rd
14.	to train them to communicate clearly and honestly	2.5759	
15.	to teach self-confidence	2.6069	
16.	to equip them with social skills	2.6207	
	Average Mean: Assertiveness Training Techniques	2.601	5th
17.	to make the most out of a safe, supportive environment for counselling	2.7069	
18.	to let the client lead the discussion in their own way	2.8448	
19.	to help create a sense of character to figure out actions	2.7379	
	Average Mean: Person-centered Therapy	2.763	1st
20.	to provide insight into the underlying causes of low self-esteem	2.6207	
21.	to discover how current situation, trigger old thinking or feelings	2.7172	
22.	to enhance the client’s self-awareness	2.5483	
	Average Mean: Psychodynamic Therapy	2.628	4th

23. to help individual gain new perception and learn valuable coping strategies	2.7069	
24. to help fostering a sense of belonging	2.6759	
25. to help challenge self-limiting beliefs thereby develop interpersonal skills	2.8621	
Average Mean: Group Therapy	2.748	2nd

Table 3 presents the means and rank order on counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State. The table indicates that items on person-centered therapy (with average mean score of 2.763), items on group therapy (with average mean score of 2.748) and items on Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (with mean score of 2.735) were ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd respectively. The items are regarded as the most counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State.

Hypotheses Testing

Three null hypotheses were postulated for this study. The hypotheses were tested using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical procedure. Significant differences were determined at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis One: *There is no significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on gender.*

Table 4: Counselling Strategies on the basis of Gender

Gender	No.	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t-val.	Crit. t-val.	p-value	Decision
Male	79	23.1646	5.28042	287	23.906	1.96	0.000	Rejected
Female	210	39.4619	5.12158					

Table 4 shows the mean, standard deviation and t-value of respondents on the basis of gender. The result on the table revealed that the calculated t-value of 23.9 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 with 287 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there was a significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State based on gender.

Hypothesis Two: *There is no significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on years in service.*

Table 5: ANOVA comparing respondents on the basis of Years in Service

Sources	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F-val.	Crit. F-val.	p-value	Decision
Between Group	16522.064	2	8261.032	370.211	3.00	0.000	Rejected
Within Group	6381.922	286	22.314				
Total	22903.986	288					

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 5 presents the calculated F-value of 370.2 which is greater than the critical F-value of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha level. And since the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected. This implies there is a significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State based on years in service. In order to determine the mean value(s) that led to the significant difference observed in the ANOVA results of Table 5, the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used as a post-hoc test. The results of the DMRT procedure are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) showing differences among respondents based on Years in Service

Years in Service	N	Mean	Duncan's Grouping	Group
11 years and above	192	40.19	A	1
6-10 years in service	61	27.32	B	2
1-5 years in service	36	20.33	C	3

Table 6 presents Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) result to show group means that led to the significant difference noted in the ANOVA result of table 5. The DMRT results indicated that group 1 with mean score of 40.19 differed significantly from group 2, with mean scores of 27.32 and greatly differed from Groups 3 with mean score of 20.33 respectively. Hence, all group are significantly different to each other. However, group 1(11 years and above) has the highest level of counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors based on years in service.

Hypothesis Three: *There is no significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by school counsellors in Kwara State based on educational qualification.*

Table 7: ANOVA comparing respondents based on Educational Qualification

Sources	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F-val.	Crit. F-val.	p-value	Decision
Between Group	544.481	2	272.241	3.482	3.00	0.032	Rejected
Within Group	22359.505	286	78.180				
Total	22903.986	288					

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

Table 7 presents the calculated F-value of 3.48 which is greater than the critical F-value of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha level. And since the p-value of 0.032 is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected. This implies there was a significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State based on Educational Qualification. In order to determine the mean value(s) that led to the significant difference observed in the ANOVA results of Table 7, the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used as a post-hoc test. The results of the DMRT procedure are displayed in

Table 8: Duncan’s Multiple Range Test (DMRT) showing differences among respondents based on Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Duncan’s Grouping	Group
3 rd Degree	4	41.66	A	1
2 nd Degree	21	39.19	B	2
1 st Degree	265	34.60	C	3

Table 8 presents Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) result to show group means that led to the significant difference noted in the ANOVA result of table 7. The DMRT results indicated that group 1 with mean score of 41.66 differed significantly from group 2, with mean scores of 39.19 and greatly differed from Groups 3 with mean score of 34.60 respectively. Hence, all group are significantly different to the other. However, group 1(3rd Degree) has the highest level of counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors in Kwara State based on Educational Qualification.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one revealed that there was a significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors based on gender. The finding is contrary to Devon (2023), who opined that the best predictor of whether a therapy is successful is the connection the counsellor and the client create or share and not the gender. The finding is in agreement with Saarnio (2010) that female counsellors are found to be more tolerant and accepting during counselling session as they display unconditional positive regards, than male counsellors who show more sensitivity to gender regarding behaviour and outlook towards clients. This implies that a female counsellor and a male counsellor have different approaches and perspective that may influence their counselling relationship and effectiveness. The male counsellors can be seen as more authoritative, have more direct and problem-solving approach while female counsellors may be more empathic, nurturing, use more listening skills and emotional validation as well as having a relational-cultural skill than male counsellors.

Hypothesis two revealed that there was a significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors based on years in service. The finding is therefore contrary to the study of Konstam,et al. (2015) that the years of work experience of counsellors do not guarantee an increase in one’s expertise and personal development in counselling practice. The finding is in line with Hoti (2019) who argued that the counsellors’ work experience or years in service to some extent increase their productivity. This implies that more experienced school counsellors

have a deeper understanding of counselling skills and strategies in enhancing in-school adolescents with low self-esteem, gain confidence in their practice as well as having ability to take on leadership roles or mentorship position.

Hypothesis three also revealed that there was no significant difference in the counselling strategies for enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents as expressed by secondary school counsellors based on educational qualification. The finding is in line with Lawal, et al. (2021), who opined that school counsellors are certified educators who help in improving students all round success by implementing the school counselling program. This implies that school counsellors with advanced degrees such as master's or doctorate degrees in guidance and counselling have a deeper understanding of adolescent development, possess advanced skills assessment, diagnosis, and treatment planning for complex issues such as low self-esteem or mental health concerns. On the other hand, the school counsellors with lesser qualifications may have limited knowledge on theoretical frameworks and research-based practices and may also rely on personal experience.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, male and female guidance counsellors differ in their opinion on the counselling strategies they use. Differences also exist in the way they enhance low self-esteem among in-school adolescents based on their years in service and educational qualifications.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings and discussion from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Seminars, workshop, conferences should be organized for secondary school counsellors to enable them utilize the various counselling strategies in enhancing low self-esteem among in-school adolescents to a great extent. These seminars/workshop/conferences may be in form of training professional development programs, continue education courses, online courses, in-service training, staff development programs, and many more. These programs will help to improve their skills, knowledge, and practice, ultimately benefiting the in-school adolescents they serve.
2. Counsellors, Teachers, Psychologists, Parents and others should help adolescents with their problems using these counselling strategies rather than punishing the adolescents.

References

- Anagbogu, M. A., & Ahiaogu, I. C. (2019). Effect of assertiveness training technique on secondary school students' low self-esteem in Olu Educational Zone, Imo State. *Global Scientific Journals*, 7(9) 1089-1106.
- Anyamene, A. & Idigun, E. (2016). Effect of cognitive behaviour therapy on low self-esteem among secondary school students. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 6(2), 143-152.

- Barida, M., Titing, H., Ramli, M., Radjah, C.I., Krisphianti, Y.D., & Alawiyan, A.Z.B. (2022). Analysis of the application of person-centered counselling in guidance and counselling services at school. *Jurnal Nusantara of Research*, 9(2), 187-202.
- Devon, F. (2023). *Should I see a male or female therapist?* <https://www.psychologytoday.com>
- Dhami, M. (2020). *The importance of guidance and counselling in adolescents' life*. Department of human development and family studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. <https://ijip.in/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/18.01.058.20231102.pdf>
- Hoti, E. (2019). Work engagement and its relationship with personality traits among teachers at the secondary level in Norway Sammenhenger. *Western Norway of applied sciences*
- Jayanthi, D., Kowsalya, N., Manju, S. (2020). Perception of JES (Job Engagement Scale) among ite/ ites employees: A study. *International Journal of scientific & Research*, 9(01), 4256-4261.
- Jones, F.C. (2012). *Low self-esteem: Indispensable self-esteem in human development*. Chicago: Defender Publishers.
- Karibi-Whyte, C. (2024). *30 Self-Esteem Group Therapy Activities: Transform Your individual*. <https://www.linkedin.com/in/chinyelu-philomena-karibi-whyte/>
- Kibuthu, J. & Muasa, W. P. (2023). Strategies for enhancing self-esteem among students in mixed secondary schools in Soweto Embakasi East Country, Nairobi, Kenya. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science* 7(8): 960-969
- Konstam, V., Cook, A., Tomek, S., Mahdavi, E., Gracia, R., & Bayne, A.H. (2015). Evidence based practices, work engagement and professional expertise of counsellors. *The Professional Counsellor*, 5(1), 67-80
- Kuboka, V. R. (2017). *Perceived paternal care and self-esteem as a major predictor of depressive symptoms among adolescent boys in selected schools in Kiambu County, Kenya*. <http://dspace.pacuniversity.ac.ke:8080/123456789/3019>.
- Lawal, A. O., Bandekaji, C. A & Ogunode, N. J. (2021). Challenges facing counsellors in Nigerian public primary schools and way forward. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 17, 2694-9970.
- Mao, Q. (2019). The effect on group counseling for the low self-Concept of undergraduate. *Open Access Library Journal*, 6, 1-8.
- Mathwasa, J. & Sibanda, L. (2020). Enhancing students' self-efficacy: implication for high school guidance and counselling educators. IntechOpen. doi:10.5772/intechopen.90555
- Nwokolo, C.N. & Oguzie, A.E. (2021). Relationship between secondary school students' self-esteem and their attitude towards examination malpractice in Imo state. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies*, 4(1), 33 – 44.
- Okafor, E.O. Obi, J.S.C. & Oguzie, A.E. (2018). Relationship between student's self-esteem and academic achievements in Imo state. *African Journal of Multi-disciplinary Research*, 1(1), 268-309.
- Okoiye, O.J., Okereke, C. & Nwoga, A, N. (2015). Effect of assertiveness training and cognitive restructuring technique on self-esteem of female undergraduate victims of relationship

violence in south-west Nigeria. *European Center of for Research and Development Psychology*, 3(2), 15-29.

Ridley, C. (2023). *Self-esteem counselling: boost your confidence and self-worth with help from Thriveworks*. <https://thriveworks.com/therapy/self-esteem-counselling/>

Saarnio, P. (2010). Big five personality traits and interpersonal functioning in female and male substance abuse therapists. *Substance use and misuse* 45(10), 1463-1473.

Sharma, S. & Agarwala, S. (2015). Self-esteem and collective self-esteem among adolescents: An interventional approach. *Psychological Thought*, 8, 105-113.

UKEssy, (2018). *The influence of gender on therapy outcomes*. <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/psychology/gender-influence-on-the-therapeutic-relationship-and-psychotherapy-psychology-essay.php?vref=1>

Woolfe, S. (2019). *Therapy for low self-esteem: how it works healthy place* <https://www.healthyplace.com/blogs/buildingself-esteem/2019/5/therapy-for-low-self-esteem-how-it-works>